

YASHIL

IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

RESPUBLIKA KONFERENSIYA (ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMAN) MAQOLA VA TEZISLAR TO'PLAMI:
"MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR SAQLASHDA
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT", "YASHIL MOLIYA",
"YASHIL BUXGALTERIYA" VA ILG'OR
MUHANDISLIK MAKTABLARINI ILMIY-AMALIY
INTEGRATSIYALASHTIRISH DOLZARBLIGI"

Konferensiya maqola va tezislari to'plami

2025-YIL
30-MAY

ROAD
74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 504 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 11-martda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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IMPROVING THE EVALUATION OF RETAIL LENDING PRACTICES EFFICIENCY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article examines the efficiency of retail lending in commercial banks of Uzbekistan, focusing on Uzsanoatqurilishbank and Aloqabank. Statistical analysis was used to identify key factors affecting retail credit performance, including household income, inflation, refinancing rate, deposits, and interest margins. The results show that lending efficiency depends on effective risk management, competitive interest policies, and digital transformation in the banking sector.

Key words: retail lending, bank margin, deposits, refinancing rate, inflation, household income, credit efficiency.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekiston tijorat banklarida chakana kreditlash samaradorligi Uzsanoatqurilishbank va Aloqabank misolida tahlil qilingan. Statistik tahlil orqali chakana kredit faoliyatiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillar — aholi daromadi, inflyatsiya, qayta moliyalash stavkasi, depozitlar va bank marjasi aniqlangan. Natijalar kredit samaradorligi risklarni boshqarish, raqobatbardosh foiz siyosati va bank tizimi raqamlashtirilishiga bog'liq ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: chakana kredit, bank marjasi, depozit, qayta moliyalash stavkasi, inflyatsiya, aholi daromadi, kredit samaradorligi.

Аннотация: В статье исследуется эффективность розничного кредитования в коммерческих банках Узбекистана на примере Uzsanoatqurilishbank и Aloqabank. С помощью статистического анализа выявлены ключевые факторы, влияющие на розничное кредитование: доходы населения, инфляция, ставка рефинансирования, депозиты и банковская маржа. Результаты показывают, что эффективность кредитования зависит от управления рисками, конкурентной процентной политики и цифровизации банковского сектора.

Ключевые слова: розничное кредитование, банковская маржа, депозиты, ставка рефинансирования, инфляция, доходы населения, эффективность кредитования.

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of credit efficiency in commercial banks can be conducted using various approaches and methods. Depending on the perspective taken toward credit efficiency, it is possible to evaluate and assess its effectiveness. Specifically:

1. Evaluating the effectiveness of the bank's credit strategies.
2. Identifying issues within the credit portfolio and taking necessary measures.
3. Determining which credit products are most significant to the bank.
4. Assessing the impact of changes in interest rates on credit operations.

The growing intensity of competition in the banking services market is leading to a reduction in the revenues of commercial banks. In particular, payment services handled by mobile operators and payment organizations, along with the rising number of producers and distributors acting as competitors to banks, negatively affect banks' efficiency indicators. Furthermore, the establishment of banks with various ownership structures in Uzbekistan and the expansion of digital technologies and online lending practices are pushing banks to compete for retail credit market customers.

By the end of 2020, the total outstanding loans provided by banks to the population in Uzbekistan amounted to 54.1 trillion UZS. Among these, 15 banks held over 1% market share and collectively accounted for 52 trillion UZS, or 96.1% of the total retail loan portfolio. Of these, Ipoteka Bank held the largest share at 18.7%.

By the end of 2022, the outstanding loan balance increased to 99.1 trillion UZS, and 19 banks held over 1% market share, collectively accounting for 96.8 trillion UZS, or 97.8% of the market. Ipoteka Bank's share of the retail credit market decreased to 15.6%, marking a decline of 3.1 percentage points compared to 2020. The development of competition can be demonstrated by the increase in the number of banks holding more than a 1% market share and by the decline in the average market share per bank—from 6.4% in 2020 to 5.1% in 2022, a decrease of 1.3 percentage points.

In addition to increasing the volume of credit provided to the population and entrepreneurs and securing a stable position in the market, commercial banks face another critical issue: ensuring the timely repayment of loans issued to clients and reducing the proportion of non-performing loans. This requires not only sustaining high growth in retail lending but also effectively managing credit risks, thereby improving the quality of the credit portfolio.

Let's examine the analytical aspects of the efficiency indicators of retail lending activities and their evaluation using the example of commercial banks.

J. Isakov (2015) concluded that "the proper and rational organization of the lending process in commercial banks positively affects credit efficiency, drives the growth of bank income, and provides opportunities to attract additional resources" [4].

A. Azlarova (2018) argued that "the ultimate goal of managing a commercial bank's credit portfolio is to achieve optimal levels of risk, profitability, and liquidity indicators for that portfolio" [1].

In M. Khayitova's research, the transformation of banks was analyzed with respect to credit efficiency, primarily through bank ranking indicators and the analysis of non-performing loans. According to the author, "the quality of strategies to improve credit efficiency in commercial banks depends entirely on the qualifications and professional competence of the bank staff actively involved in their implementation" [8].

A. B. Kalandarov maintains that reducing non-performing loans in commercial banks enables more efficient management of the credit portfolio [6].

Building on the perspectives and literature of these authors and researchers, we offer our own view on evaluating banks' credit efficiency. Credit efficiency evaluation is a systematic analysis of a bank's credit portfolio aimed at improving loan quality, ensuring higher income, and identifying directions for lending improvements.

Analyzing lending activities in commercial banks helps to identify potential problems related to credit and to decide whether to continue lending to a borrower, require collateral, or take other measures. It also enables continuous monitoring of the bank's mission, strategy, and business plan targets.

This study employs grouping, comparative and structural analysis, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, and other scientific cognition methods. Additionally, using an OLS regression model, we analyze practical data on retail lending activities of commercial banks operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan, assessing the reliability of factors affecting retail lending and their interrelationships.

The dynamics of growth in retail lending services to the population by commercial banks have outpaced both previous years and the overall growth rate of total credit placements. In recent years, the activity of newly established private banks in the retail services market has further increased.

Table 1. Changes in the Outstanding Balance of Loans to Individuals by Commercial Banks of the Republic of Uzbekista (billion soums)

Indicator	01.01.2020	01.01.2021	01.01.2022	01.01.23
Outstanding balance of loans to individuals	39 934	54 888	69 496	100 949
Mortgage loans	20 326	28 301	35 946	46 460
Consumer loans	3 177	5 737	9 429	25 234
Micro-loans	5 492	12 237	12 795	14 651
Micro-loans for the business activities of individuals	6 467	8 613	11 326	14 567
Other loans	4 472	0	0	36
Total loan placements	211 581	276 975	326 386	390 049
Share of retail loans in total loan placements, %	19%	20%	21%	26%

The terms of loans provided to individuals by commercial banks, their increasing accessibility, and the reduction of various barriers in the lending process have all contributed to the growth in the volume of lending. This is confirmed by the fact that the outstanding balance of loans issued to individuals by commercial banks in 2022 amounted to 100,949 billion soums — 1.45 times, or 31,453 billion soums, higher than in 2021 (69,496 billion soums).

When analyzing the efficiency indicators of retail banking activities, it is important to assess the average weighted interest rates on loans both attracted from and issued to individuals, as well as the bank margin.

Table 2. Dynamics of the bank margin on loans attracted from and issued to individuals by commercial banks

Indicators	31.12.18	31.12.19	31.12.20	31.12.21	31.12.22	Changes
JSC «Uzsanoatqurilish»						
Average interest rate on retail loans	15,9%	16,6%	14,7%	13,5%	16,3%	0,4%
Average interest rate on retail deposits	7,7%	4,6%	3,4%	7,5%	13,2%	5,5%
Bank margin	8,2%	11,9%	11,3%	6,0%	3,1%	-5,1%
JSC «Aloqabank»						
Average interest rate on retail loans	19,0%	20,2%	19,7%	22,4%	22,9%	3,9%
Average interest rate on retail deposits	5,8%	6,7%	8,4%	9,3%	13,0%	7,1%
Банк маржаси	13,2%	13,5%	11,3%	13,2%	9,9%	-3,3%

Commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan are taking measures to attract clients by increasing deposit interest rates and decreasing lending rates amid growing competition in the retail credit services market and efforts to mobilize financial resources. According to analytical data, Uzsanoatqurilishbank achieved a high interest margin of 11.9% by the end of 2019. However, a declining trend has been observed, with the margin dropping to 3.1% as of January 1, 2023. Aloqabank's interest margin has been unstable, reaching its peak of 13.5% at the end of 2019, but overall, the analysis period indicates a downward trend.

Commercial banks are attracting deposits at high interest rates. Despite the fact that today commercial banks offer deposits for individuals in the national currency at an annual rate of up to 24%, the average interest rate on deposits attracted from individuals remained low at 13% in 2022. This can be attributed to the funds held on population bank cards and in demand deposits.

Assessing the efficiency of retail lending by major commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan and analyzing the influencing factors is of significant importance. In the course of this research, we conduct a statistical analysis of the retail loan portfolios and their determining factors for Uzsanoatqurilishbank JSCB and Aloqabank JSCB.

Based on this statistical analysis, we construct a functional model of the influencing factors as follows:

$$F(RL_AVR) = X(RL, RD, BA, R_per_income, PR, IR, PINCOME)$$

The following variables were selected for statistical analysis:

- Y – RL_AVR – average weighted interest rate on retail loans;
- X₁ – RL – retail loan portfolio balance;
- X₂ – RD – balance of deposits attracted from individuals;
- X₃ – BA – bank's net asset balance;
- X₄ – R_per_income – interest income received from retail loans;
- X₅ – PR – refinancing rate of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- X₆ – IR – inflation rate;
- X₇ – PINCOME – population income.

	RL_AVR	RL	RD	BA	R_per_income	PR	IR	PINCOME
RL_AVR	1.00	0.56	0.43	0.45	0.54	0.79	0.38	0.44
RL	0.56	1.00	0.96	0.98	1.00	0.68	-0.11	0.97
RD	0.43	0.96	1.00	0.97	0.95	0.60	-0.16	0.98
BA	0.45	0.98	0.97	1.00	0.97	0.60	-0.08	0.99
R_per_income	0.54	1.00	0.95	0.97	1.00	0.68	-0.15	0.95
PR	0.79	0.68	0.60	0.60	0.68	1.00	0.26	0.55
IR	0.38	-0.11	-0.16	-0.08	-0.15	0.26	1.00	-0.14
PINCOME	0.44	0.97	0.98	0.99	0.95	0.55	-0.14	1.00

Picture 1. Correlation analysis of factors influencing the retail lending activity of Uzsanotqurilishbank JSCB

The degree of interrelation among factors affecting the retail lending activity of Uzsanotqurilishbank JSCB for the period 2010–2022 has been assessed. The analysis reveals a strong correlation (0.79) between the average weighted interest rate on the bank’s retail loans and the refinancing rate set by the Central Bank. However, the correlation between the average weighted interest rate on retail loans and the interest income generated from these loans is relatively low (0.54), suggesting a high proportion of preferential loans within the bank’s portfolio. Moreover, the retail loan portfolio shows a strong correlation with individual deposits (0.96), the bank’s total assets (0.98), and household income levels (0.97), indicating that these factors significantly influence the volume of retail lending.

The results of the statistical analysis indicate that the reliability level of the observed factors influencing Uzsanotqurilishbank JSCB’s retail lending activity over the period 2010–2022 is high, with an R-squared value of 0.94. This suggests that the model explains 94% of the variability in retail lending activity. In the statistical model, the ($P>|t|$) value indicates the predictive significance of each variable. The analysis shows that household income, inflation rate, and the bank’s total assets have the most significant impact on the retail lending operations of Uzsanotqurilishbank JSCB.

A strong correlation is also observed between the average weighted interest rate on retail loans and the Central Bank’s refinancing rate (0.77), as well as with interest income from retail loans (0.95). Furthermore, the average weighted interest rate on retail loans shows a strong correlation with the retail loan portfolio balance (0.92), individual deposits (0.81), bank assets (0.94), and household income (0.91), indicating that these factors are closely linked to the dynamics of the bank’s retail lending operations.

The results of the statistical analysis show that the reliability level (0.99) of the factors observed in the retail lending activities of JSC “Aloqabank” from 2010 to 2022 was high. In the statistical model, the indicator ($P>|t|$) is calculated to determine the statistical predictive significance of each factor. This indicator shows that the statistical significance of the observed indicators in JSC “Aloqabank”’s retail lending activities is high. In the analysis, a $P>|t|$ value of less than 0.05 indicates high statistical significance for the variables considered.

Research has been conducted on improving the efficiency of lending activities by commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The analysis primarily focused on the overall portfolio performance indicators of banks.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study on retail lending efficiency in commercial banks of Uzbekistan shows that the quality of credit portfolios largely depends on the management of risks, income stability, and the macroeconomic environment. Statistical analysis of Uzsanotqurilishbank and Aloqabank confirmed a strong interrelation between retail lending performance and factors such as household income, inflation, deposits, and the refinancing rate.

In addition, the research highlights that improving lending efficiency requires not only sound financial management but also digital transformation and customer-oriented innovation in banking operations. The integration of advanced analytics, automated credit scoring systems, and flexible loan products can significantly enhance decision-making accuracy and reduce credit risks. Strengthening institutional capacity and ensuring transparency in credit procedures will further contribute to sustainable growth in the retail lending sector.

Recommendations:

1. Introduce more flexible and data-driven credit scoring systems.
2. Strengthen monitoring of non-performing loans (NPLs).

3. Enhance the use of digital lending platforms to improve accessibility and efficiency.
4. Optimize the interest margin by balancing deposit and loan rates.
5. Improve financial literacy programs to support responsible borrowing.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025-yil, may.

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>